

What is consciousness at 50% gasocrine signaling?

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What is consciousness is a major question in biology and various cultures (1–3). The concept of consciousness has even been extended to larger scales with the term “global consciousness” (4). For the sake of discussion, I define human consciousness as the ability to integrate information while being self-aware (5). In the first postulate of the gasocrine signaling hypotheses, I stated that *All living organisms composed of one or more cells require gasocrine signaling to sense, communicate, survive and propagate* (6). According to this postulate, without gasocrine signaling, there would be no consciousness. However, this does not explain consciousness (or does it metaphorically?). Rather than asking what consciousness is, let’s probe the question: What is consciousness for a human when gasocrine signaling functions at only 50%?

In the emerging field of gasocrinology, all the gases (and perhaps even volatiles) are ligands that mediate gasocrine signaling (7, 8, 6). All proteins whose activity is affected by the binding or unbinding of these gases are gasoreceptors that trigger gasocrine signaling. It is also important to consider other classes of gas-sensing receptors, such as riboceptors and etc., (9). What would happen to human consciousness if (local) gasocrine signaling were reduced by 50%? To perform such an experiment on humans in the treatment group, (in normal atmospheric pressure environment), one must reduce all exterior and interior gases (and perhaps volatiles) by 50%, or alternatively, reduce the activity of all gasoreceptors by 50%. However, there is a paradox in the ligand-focused experiment. How does one not affect the pressure while reducing all the gases by 50% in the environment of the treatment group? There is also a potential pitfall in the receptor-focused experiment. How can we be sure that inhibiting or removing 50% of the gasoreceptors will not cause other previously classified non-gasoreceptor proteins or nucleic acids to act as gasoreceptors, riboceptors, or deoxyriboceptors? Let’s consider the effects of altering only one gasocrine signaling ligand: dioxygen. Would a human remain conscious if the fraction of inspired dioxygen (FiO_2) were 0.105 instead of 0.210? Perhaps some cognitive activities will remain, but what if the FiO_2 is set below 0.1 or to 0 in an acute or chronic manner? A parallel experiment targeting gasoreceptors would abruptly inhibit 50% or 90% or 100% of dioxygen-sensing gasoreceptor, riboceptors, and etc. This would also include inhibiting (putative) dioxygen protogasoreceptors and gasoreceptor, such as hemoglobin, its paralogs, and etc., (10). What will the state of consciousness be for the humans in the treatment groups? Will their brains be able to integrate information while remaining self-aware?

Overall, based on the thought experiments and their implications listed above, human (and perhaps global) consciousness possibly arises from, the sum of gasocrine signaling activities.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

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REFERENCES

1. **Crick F, Koch C.** Some reflections on visual awareness. *Cold Spring Harb Symp Quant Biol* 55: 953–962, 1990. doi: 10.1101/sqb.1990.055.01.089.
2. **Seth AK, Bayne T.** Theories of consciousness. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 23: 439–452, 2022. doi: 10.1038/s41583-022-00587-4.
3. **Lind RE.** *The Seat of Consciousness in Ancient Literature*. McFarland, 2015.
4. **Zhang RJ, Liu JH, Lee M, Lin M, Xie T, Chen SX, Leung AK -y., Lee I-C, Hodgetts D, Valdes EA, Choi SY.** Continuities and discontinuities in the cultural evolution of global consciousness. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 379: 20220263, 2023. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2022.0263.
5. **Tononi G, Koch C.** Consciousness: here, there and everywhere? *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci* 370: 20140167, 2015. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2014.0167.
6. **Anbalagan S.** Gasocrine signaling hypotheses [Online]. Zenodo: 2025. <https://zenodo.org/records/13690909> [23 Aug. 2025].
7. **Aono S.** *Gas Sensing in Cells*. Royal Society of Chemistry, 2017.
8. **Anbalagan S.** Heme-based oxygen gasoreceptors. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab* 326: E178–E181, 2024. doi: 10.1152/ajpendo.00004.2024.
9. **Anbalagan S.** Gas-sensing riboceptors. *RNA Biol* 21: 1–6, 2024. doi: 10.1080/15476286.2024.2379607.
10. **Anbalagan S.** Vertebrate hemoglobin - a dioxygen transporter or protogasoreceptor? [Online]. Zenodo: 2025. <https://zenodo.org/records/16724347> [23 Aug. 2025].